

Description of software I2VIS, version for modeling of the relamination process

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1 Methods

1.1 Governing equations

For computations we use software I2VIS that solves the equations of continuity, motion, and heat transport using a finite-volume scheme on a fully staggered grid in two dimensions in combination with the particle-in-cell method (*Gerya and Yuen, 2003*). The equations of conservation of momentum and mass assume compressible material and negligible inertia:

$$\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} + \frac{D \ln \rho_{\text{eff}}}{Dt} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial P}{\partial x}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{yx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yy}}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial P}{\partial y} - g \rho_{\text{eff}}, \quad (3)$$

where x and y are the Eulerian coordinates (y increases downward), v_x , v_y are the components of the velocity vector, σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} , σ_{xy} are the components of the deviatoric stress tensor, P is the pressure, g is the gravity and ρ_{eff} is the effective density.

The equation of heat transport includes the radiogenic, adiabatic and shear heating sources:

$$\rho_{\text{eff}} c_p \frac{DT}{Dt} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) = H_r - T \alpha \rho v_y g + \sigma_{xx} \dot{\epsilon}_{xx} + 2 \sigma_{xy} \dot{\epsilon}_{xy} + \sigma_{yy} \dot{\epsilon}_{yy}, \quad (4)$$

where c_p is the heat capacity, T is the temperature, t is the time, k is the thermal conductivity, H_r is the radiogenic heating, α is the thermal expansivity and $\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}$, $\dot{\epsilon}_{yy}$, $\dot{\epsilon}_{xy}$ are the components of the deviatoric strain-rate tensor.

1.2 Material properties

Lagrangian particles are used to track the heterogeneous composition of material in the model domain. The effective values of the material parameters in the governing equations (1)-(4) are interpolated from the values calculated for the individual particles depending on their material type (*Gerya and Yuen, 2003*).

For each material type, the density depends on temperature and pressure:

$$\rho_{PT} = \rho_0 [1 - \alpha(T - T_0)] [1 + \beta(P - P_0)] \chi_\rho, \quad (5)$$

where ρ_0 is the reference density of the given rock type at temperature $T = T_0$ and pressure $P = P_0$, α is the thermal expansivity and β is the compressibility. The coefficient χ_ρ represents changes of the density due to phase transitions. The phase transitions occur in the modeled mafic continental crust, oceanic crust and mantle. The mafic continental and oceanic crust are affected by the transformations of basalt to garnet granulite and eclogite (density increase by 16%) (*Ito and Kennedy, 1971*) and spinel to perovskite (density increase by 8%) (*Ito et al., 1990; Mishin et al., 2008*). In the mantle, transformations of olivine to spinel (density increase by 6%) and perovskite (density increase by 11%) are taken into account (*Katsura and Ito, 1989; Ito et al., 1990*). At low temperatures ($T < T_{\max}$), slow reaction kinetics hinder the phase transitions: $\chi_\rho = 1$ for $T < T_{\min}$ and χ_ρ varies linearly from 1 to the kinetics-independent value between $T = T_{\min}$ and $T = T_{\max}$. The thermal conductivity, melting temperatures and latent heat of melting are calculated from values in Table 2.

The rheology is expressed via the effective viscosity η_{eff} :

$$\sigma_{xx} = 2\eta_{\text{eff}}\dot{\epsilon}_{xx}, \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = 2\eta_{\text{eff}}\dot{\epsilon}_{xy}, \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} = 2\eta_{\text{eff}}\dot{\epsilon}_{yy}, \quad (8)$$

which is calculated according to the viscoplastic rheology. The viscous behavior (the viscosity η_v) is a combination of dislocation (η_{dis}), diffusion (η_{dif}) and Peierls creep (η_{pei}):

$$\eta_v = \min \left[(1/\eta_{\text{dis}} + 1/\eta_{\text{dif}})^{-1}, \eta_{\text{pei}} \right]. \quad (9)$$

The following flow laws are applied: (i) dislocation creep:

$$\eta_{\text{dis}} = \frac{1}{2} A^{-1} \dot{\epsilon}_{\text{II}}^{\frac{1-n}{n}} \exp \left(\frac{E_A + V_A P}{nRT} \right), \quad (10)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_{\text{II}}$ is the second invariant of the deviatoric strain rate tensor, A is the prefactor, n is the stress exponent, E_A is the activation energy, V_A is the activation volume and R is the gas constant, (ii) diffusion creep for a constant grain size:

$$\eta_{\text{dif}} = \frac{1}{2} A^{-1} \exp \left(\frac{E_A + V_A P}{RT} \right), \quad (11)$$

and (iii) Peierls creep:

$$\eta_{\text{pei}} = A^{-1} \sigma_{\text{II}}^{-1} \exp \left(\frac{E_A + V_A P}{RT} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_{\text{II}}}{\sigma_{\text{pei}}} \right)^2 \right), \quad (12)$$

where σ_{II} is the second invariant of the stress tensor and σ_{pei} is the Peierls stress. Parameter values are specified in Table 3.

The plastic behavior approximates the brittle failure of the rock. When combined with the viscous behavior it effectively limits the viscosity so that the yield strength of the rock is never exceeded:

$$\eta_{\text{vp}} = \min \left(\eta_v, \frac{\sigma_y}{2\dot{\epsilon}_{\text{II}}} \right), \quad (13)$$

where the yield strength σ_y is given by the Drucker-Prager yield criterion:

$$\sigma_y = C + \phi P_{\text{eff}}, \quad (14)$$

where C is the cohesion and ϕ is the internal friction coefficient, which depends of the total plastic strain. We assume that ϕ decreases linearly from the initial to the final value between the plastic strain ϵ_0 and ϵ_1 (e.g. *Pysklywec et al.*, 2002). P_{eff} is the effective pressure which equals dynamic pressure P for solid rocks without free water and is lowered in the presence of fluids or melt.

1.3 Erosion and sedimentation

The model domain is rectangular and has a fixed shape. The deforming surface of the Earth is modeled using a "sticky-air" method (*Schmeling et al.*, 2008; *Crameri et al.*, 2012). The "sticky air" is a low-density low-viscosity material representing air or water above the rocky interior of the Earth. The position of the interface between the "sticky-air" and the "rock" corresponds to the surface topography y_e . Erosion and sedimentation operate at this interface and modify the topography (*Gorczyk et al.*, 2007). Erosion operates only for the topography at least h_e above the sea level. For these topography highs, the erosion rate v_e is constant. Similarly, sedimentation at a constant rate v_s is applied only in topography lows, where the topography is below the sea level. In regions with a slope higher than α_e , additional surface relaxation is applied to avoid extreme steepening of the slope.

1.4 Water and melt

At the beginning of the model evolution, some materials (sediments and oceanic crust) contain a certain fraction of water (X_{w0} , see Table 2). The maximum water content that can be retained in the rock decreases linearly with depth and temperature, mimicking compaction and dehydration reactions:

$$X_w = X_{w0} \frac{T_{w,\text{max}} - T}{T_{w,\text{max}} - T_0} \frac{y_{w,\text{max}} - y + y_e}{y_{w,\text{max}}} \quad (15)$$

where $T_{w,\text{max}}$ and $y_{w,\text{max}}$ are the maximum temperature and depth, respectively, at which water can be retained in the rock (*Gerya et al.*, 2002). The excess water is released as a fluid particle that migrates with a constant vertical velocity v_{w0} with respect to the rock until it reaches material that can consume it according to eq. (15).

Melting in crustal material is parametrized using the solidus and liquidus temperatures, T_{solid} and T_{liquid} , respectively (Table 2). The volumetric fraction of melt X_{m0} that can be produced by the rock increases linearly between T_{solid} and T_{liquid} :

$$\begin{aligned} X_{m0} &= \frac{T - T_{\text{solid}}}{T_{\text{liquid}} - T_{\text{solid}}} \quad \text{if } T_{\text{solid}} < T < T_{\text{liquid}}, \\ X_{m0} &= 0 \quad \text{if } T < T_{\text{solid}}, \\ X_{m0} &= 1 \quad \text{if } T > T_{\text{liquid}}. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

For melting of the mantle, a more complex approach is adopted where X_{m0} depends on pressure and water content (*Katz et al.*, 2003).

Only a limited amount of melt can be retained in the rock. Once the melt fraction X_m exceeds the threshold X_{\max} , a part of the melt $X_{\text{ext}} = X_m - X_{\min}$ is released while the fraction X_{\min} remains in the source rock. A part of water proportional to X_{ext} is extracted together with the melt and therefore removed from the rock. The melt fraction present in the rock X_m depends of the total extracted melt during the previous evolution $\sum X_{\text{ext}}$:

$$X_m = X_{m0} - \sum X_{\text{ext}}. \quad (17)$$

Melt is extracted in batches represented by melt particles. It migrates instantaneously in the model time scale and the melt particles are therefore emplaced above the site of melt extraction, where they form either volcanic or plutonic rocks (*Vogt et al.*, 2012). Volcanics form just below the surface, while plutonic rocks are emplaced at a larger depth in the site of the highest intrusion emplacement rate determined by evaluating locally the ratio of the effective melt overpressure to the effective viscosity of the crust (*Vogt et al.*, 2012).

The presence of water and melt modifies the effective viscosity of the rock. Hydrated mantle ($X_w > 0$) and partially molten rocks ($T > T_{\text{solid}}$) deform according to weaker flow laws (hydrated mantle) and with a lower internal friction (zero ϕ in molten rocks). In addition, the effective pressure in hydrated rocks is reduced: $P_{\text{eff}} = P\lambda_f$. Similarly, during melt extraction, P_{eff} in the column between the source of the melt and the site of melt emplacement is decreased according to $P_{\text{eff}} = P\lambda_m$. This decrease of the effective pressure mimics weakening by the magma rising to the surface in dikes (*Gerya et al.*, 2015). In the presence of both melt and fluids, $P_{\text{eff}} = P \min(\lambda_m, \lambda_f)$. The effective density ρ_{eff} of rocks is also corrected for the presence of melt and water. Effective densities of partially-molten and hydrated rocks are calculated as weighted averages of the densities of their solid and fluid components.

The latent heat of melting is accounted for by an increased effective heat capacity $c_{p,\text{eff}}$ and thermal expansion α_{eff} of the partially molten rocks, calculated as (*Gerya et al.*, 2008):

$$\begin{aligned} c_{p,\text{eff}} &= c_p + H_L \left(\frac{\partial X_m}{\partial T} \right)_P, \\ \alpha_{\text{eff}} &= \alpha + \frac{\rho H_L}{T} \left(\frac{\partial X_m}{\partial P} \right)_T, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where c_p and α are the heat capacity and the thermal expansion of the solid rock, respectively, and H_L is the latent heat of melting (Table 2).

2 Limitations of the two-dimensional setup

The choice of the two-dimensional (2D) Cartesian geometry imposes important limitations on the model applicability to natural subduction-collision systems. In such models, the complex interaction of the plates moving on the globe and their coupling with mantle convection is lacking. As a result, the plate velocities do not evolve self-consistently and boundary conditions that have to be defined significantly affect the model evolution. The usual choices of boundary conditions are: (i) no imposed plate velocities and purely buoyancy-driven motion that neglects far-field plate-tectonic forces and that may overestimate the effect of mantle phase transitions, or (ii) prescribed velocities of the plates that crudely approximate the effect of far-field plate-tectonic forces and that may induce unrealistic stresses in the plates. Both these possibilities are commonly used in numerical models of subduction-collision processes (e.g. *Duretz et al.*, 2011; *Sizova et al.*, 2012; *Tetreault and Buitter*, 2012).

A major limitation of 2D models is that they cannot capture an oblique convergence of plates, a common situation in nature. Oblique convergence effectively reduces the velocity of subduction and it may also lead to diachroneity of collision along the trench. However, the dynamic effects of oblique convergence are much broader, including along-trench stress variations, development of strike-slip faults or trench-parallel propagation of tearing of the subducted slab (*Díaz-Azpiroz et al.*, 2016, and references therein). 3D models that can appropriately simulate these features and their dynamics began to appear only recently (e.g. *Balázs et al.*, 2021; *Andrić-Tomašević et al.*, 2023).

In addition, the inherited architecture of plates (and of the underlying mantle) is 3D in nature. Variations of properties of the plates along the trench cannot be captured in a 2D model. As a first order estimate of the effect of these variations, it is possible to vary properties of the 2D models and compare the resulting model evolutions. However, some features that occur in plate-convergent settings are 3D by definition (e.g. trench-parallel strike-slip faults). These tectonic features cannot be prescribed nor naturally develop in 2D models. Other features may be approximated in 2D (e.g. diapiric upwellings; (*Hasenclever et al.*, 2011)), but would have different shapes than in 3D, which would change the dynamics of their deformational and thermal evolution. With all their limitations, 2D numerical modelling studies have provided significant insight into the dynamics of subduction and collision of plates. Therefore, 2D models are still a valuable tool if they are interpreted with caution.

Table 1: Values of model parameters.

symbol	meaning	value, unit
α	thermal expansivity	$2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{K}^{-1}$; zero in air and water (M0, M1)
α_e	topography slope where intense erosion starts	17°
β	compressibility	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{MPa}^{-1}$; zero in air and water (M0, M1)
C	cohesion	1 MPa
c_p	heat capacity	$1000 \text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
ϵ_0	strain where softening starts	0
ϵ_1	strain where softening ends	1
η_{\min}	minimum viscosity	10^{18}Pa s ; 10^{17}Pa s in air and water (M0, M1)
η_{\max}	maximum viscosity	10^{26}Pa s
g	gravity acceleration	9.81ms^{-2}
h_e	height a.s.l. where erosion begins to operate	0.5 km
H_L	latent heat of melting	— kJ kg^{-1} ; see Table 2
H_R	radiogenic heat sources	— W m^{-3} ; see Table 2
λ_f	fluid induced weakening coefficient	10^{-2}
λ_m	melt induced weakening coefficient	10^{-3}
k	thermal conductivity	— $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$; see Table 2
ρ_0	reference density	— kg m^{-3}
T_{\min}	temperature for kinetics of phase transition	$400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in mafic continental crust
T_{\max}	temperature for kinetics of phase transition	$600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in mafic continental crust
T_0	reference temperature	$0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
T_{liquid}	liquidus temperature	— K; see Table 2
T_{solid}	solidus temperature	— K; see Table 2
$T_{w,\max}$	maximum temperature for water in rock	1700 K
v_e	erosion rate	$3 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ms}^{-1}$
v_s	sedimentation rate	$3 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ms}^{-1}$
v_{w0}	velocity of percolating water	10cm yr^{-1}
X_{\min}	unextractable melt fraction	0.02
X_{\max}	maximum melt fraction retained in rock	0.04
X_{w0}	initial fluid content in rock	— wt%; see Table 2
ϕ_0, ϕ_1	initial and final internal friction coefficient	—
y_{e0}	water level	18 km from upper boundary of the model domain
$y_{w,\max}$	maximum depth for water in rock	200 km

Table 2: Material properties. Latent heat of melting is according to *Bittner and Schmeling* (1995) and *Turcotte and Schubert* (2002). Thermal conductivity is calculated as $k = (k_0 + k_1/(T_{(K)} + 77)) \exp(4 \cdot 10^{-11} P_{(\text{Pa})}) \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$; parameter values are according to *Clauser et al.* (1995). Solidus and liquidus temperatures: ¹*Poli and Schmidt* (2002) for sediments; ²*Poli and Schmidt* (2002) for sediments increased by 200 K; ³*Hess* (1989) for dry basalt; ⁴*Poli and Schmidt* (2002) for wet mid-ocean ridge basalt; ⁵*Johannes* (1985) for dry granite; ⁶Mantle melting is calculated using the approach by *Katz et al.* (2003).

material	X_{w0} wt%	T_{solid} ref.	T_{liquid} ref.	H_L kJ kg ⁻¹	H_R μWm^{-3}	k_0 W Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	k_1 Wm ⁻¹
air	—	—	—	—	—	200	0
water	—	—	—	—	—	200	0
sediments	2	1	5	300	2.0	0.64	807
felsic crust	0	2	5	300	1.0	0.64	807
mafic crust	0	3	3	380	0.25	1.18	474
basalt	2	4	3	380	0.25	1.18	474
gabbro	0	3	3	380	0.25	1.18	474
molten sediments	2	—	—	300	2.0	0.64	807
molten felsic crust	2	—	—	300	1.0	0.64	807
molten mafic crust, basalt and gabbro	2	—	—	380	0.25	1.18	474
mantle							
– dry	0	6	6	400	0.022	0.73	1293
– hydrated	2	6	6	400	0.022	0.73	1293
molten	2	—	—	400	0.022	0.73	1293

Table 3: Creep parameters. ¹*Ranalli (1995)*; ²*Ranalli and Murphy (1987)*; ³*Wilks and Carter (1990)*; ⁴*Karato and Wu (1993)* where prefactor A is calculated for the grain size of 1 mm, $m=2.5$, Burgers vector length 0.5 nm and shear modulus 80 GPa; ⁵*Evans and Goetze (1979)*; *Katayama and Karato (2008)*; ⁶*Hilaireret et al. (2007)*.

Flow law	Type	A ($\text{Pa}^{-n}\text{s}^{-1}$)	n	E_A (kJ mol^{-1})	V_A ($\text{m}^3\text{mol}^{-1}$)	σ_{pei} (MPa)	ref.
wet quartz	dislocation	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-18}$	2.3	154	$3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	1
dry quartz	dislocation	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-20}$	2.4	156	$3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	2
felsic granulite	dislocation	$8.0 \cdot 10^{-23}$	3.1	243	$3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	3
anorthite	dislocation	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-23}$	3.2	238	$8 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	1
dry olivine	dislocation	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-16}$	3.5	540	$20 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	4
dry olivine	diffusion	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-11}$	—	300	$4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	4
wet olivine	dislocation	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-15}$	3.0	430	$10 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	4
wet olivine	diffusion	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-11}$	—	240	$4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	—	4
all mantle rocks	Peierls	$6.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.0	540	$20 \cdot 10^{-6}$	9.1	4,5

References

- Andrić-Tomašević, N., A. Koptev, G. Maiti, T. Gerya, and T. A. Ehlers, Slab tearing in non-collisional settings: Insights from thermo-mechanical modelling of oblique subduction, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 610, 118,097, 2023.
- Balázs, A., C. Faccenna, K. Ueda, F. Funiciello, A. Boutoux, E. J.-P. Blanc, and T. Gerya, Oblique subduction and mantle flow control on upper plate deformation: 3d geodynamic modeling, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 569, 117,056, 2021.
- Bittner, D., and H. Schmeling, Numerical modelling of melting processes and induced diapirism in the lower crust, *Geophysical Journal International*, 123(1), 59–70, 1995.
- Clauser, C., E. Huenges, et al., Thermal conductivity of rocks and minerals, *Rock physics and phase relations: a handbook of physical constants*, 3, 105–126, 1995.
- Cramer, F., H. Schmeling, G. Golabek, T. Duretz, R. Orendt, S. Buitert, D. May, B. Kaus, T. Gerya, and P. Tackley, A comparison of numerical surface topography calculations in geodynamic modelling: an evaluation of the ‘sticky air’ method, *Geophysical Journal International*, 189(1), 38–54, 2012.
- Díaz-Azpiroz, M., S. Brune, K. A. Leever, C. Fernández, and D. M. Czeck, Tectonics of oblique plate boundary systems, *Tectonophysics*, 693, 165–170, 2016.
- Duretz, T., T. V. Gerya, and D. A. May, Numerical modelling of spontaneous slab breakoff and subsequent topographic response, *Tectonophysics*, 502(1-2), 244–256, 2011.
- Evans, B., and C. Goetze, The temperature variation of hardness of olivine and its implication for polycrystalline yield stress, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 84(B10), 5505–5524, 1979.
- Gerya, T., L. Perchuk, and J.-P. Burg, Transient hot channels: perpetrating and regurgitating ultrahigh-pressure, high-temperature crust–mantle associations in collision belts, *Lithos*, 103(1-2), 236–256, 2008.
- Gerya, T. V., and D. A. Yuen, Characteristics-based marker-in-cell method with conservative finite-differences schemes for modeling geological flows with strongly variable transport properties, *Physics of the Earth and Planetary Interiors*, 140(4), 293–318, 2003.
- Gerya, T. V., B. Stöckhert, and A. L. Perchuk, Exhumation of high-pressure metamorphic rocks in a subduction channel: A numerical simulation, *Tectonics*, 21(6), 6–1, 2002.
- Gerya, T. V., R. J. Stern, M. Baes, S. V. Sobolev, and S. A. Whattam, Plate tectonics on the Earth triggered by plume-induced subduction initiation, *Nature*, 527(7577), 221–225, 2015.
- Gorczyk, W., A. P. Willner, T. V. Gerya, J. A. Connolly, and J.-P. Burg, Physical controls of magmatic productivity at Pacific-type convergent margins: Numerical modelling, *Physics of the Earth and Planetary Interiors*, 163(1-4), 209–232, 2007.

- Hasenclever, J., J. P. Morgan, M. Hort, and L. H. Rüpke, 2d and 3d numerical models on compositionally buoyant diapirs in the mantle wedge, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, *311*(1-2), 53–68, 2011.
- Hess, P. C., *Origins of igneous rocks*, vol. 336, Harvard University Press Cambridge, 1989.
- Hilaret, N., B. Reynard, Y. Wang, I. Daniel, S. Merkel, N. Nishiyama, and S. Petitgirard, High-pressure creep of serpentine, interseismic deformation, and initiation of subduction, *Science*, *318*(5858), 1910–1913, 2007.
- Ito, E., M. Akaogi, L. Topor, and A. Navrotsky, Negative pressure-temperature slopes for reactions formign MgSiO₃ perovskite from calorimetry, *Science*, *249*(4974), 1275–1278, 1990.
- Ito, K., and G. C. Kennedy, An experimental study of the basalt-garnet granulite-eclogite transition, *The structure and physical properties of the Earth's crust*, *14*, 303–314, 1971.
- Johannes, W., The significance of experimental studies for the formation of migmatites, *Migmatites*, pp. 36–85, 1985.
- Karato, S., and P. Wu, Rheology of the upper mantle: A synthesis, *Science*, *260*(5109), 771–778, 1993.
- Katayama, I., and S. Karato, Low-temperature, high-stress deformation of olivine under water-saturated conditions, *Physics of the Earth and Planetary Interiors*, *168*(3-4), 125–133, 2008.
- Katsura, T., and E. Ito, The system Mg₂SiO₄-Fe₂SiO₄ at high pressures and temperatures: Precise determination of stabilities of olivine, modified spinel, and spinel, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, *94*(B11), 15,663–15,670, 1989.
- Katz, R. F., M. Spiegelman, and C. H. Langmuir, A new parameterization of hydrous mantle melting, *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems*, *4*(9), 2003.
- Mishin, Y. A., T. V. Gerya, J.-P. Burg, and J. A. Connolly, Dynamics of double subduction: Numerical modeling, *Physics of the Earth and Planetary Interiors*, *171*(1-4), 280–295, 2008.
- Poli, S., and M. W. Schmidt, Petrology of subducted slabs, *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, *30*(1), 207–235, 2002.
- Pysklywec, R. N., C. Beaumont, and P. Fullsack, Lithospheric deformation during the early stages of continental collision: Numerical experiments and comparison with South Island, New Zealand, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, *107*(B7), doi:10.1029/2001JB000252, 2002.
- Ranalli, G., *Rheology of the Earth*, Springer Science & Business Media, 1995.
- Ranalli, G., and D. C. Murphy, Rheological stratification of the lithosphere, *Tectonophysics*, *132*(4), 281–295, 1987.

- Schmeling, H., A. Babeyko, A. Enns, C. Faccenna, F. Funiciello, T. Gerya, G. Golabek, S. Grigull, B. Kaus, G. Morra, et al., A benchmark comparison of spontaneous subduction models—Towards a free surface, *Physics of the Earth and Planetary Interiors*, 171(1-4), 198–223, 2008.
- Sizova, E., T. Gerya, and M. Brown, Exhumation mechanisms of melt-bearing ultrahigh pressure crustal rocks during collision of spontaneously moving plates, *Journal of Metamorphic Geology*, 30(9), 927–955, 2012.
- Tetreault, J., and S. Buiter, Geodynamic models of terrane accretion: Testing the fate of island arcs, oceanic plateaus, and continental fragments in subduction zones, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 117(B8), 2012.
- Turcotte, D. L., and G. Schubert, *Geodynamics*, Cambridge university press, 2002.
- Vogt, K., T. V. Gerya, and A. Castro, Crustal growth at active continental margins: numerical modeling, *Physics of the Earth and Planetary Interiors*, 192, 1–20, 2012.
- Wilks, K. R., and N. L. Carter, Rheology of some continental lower crustal rocks, *Tectonophysics*, 182(1-2), 57–77, 1990.